

1 **PPP1R16B is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and
7 at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of *PPP1R16B*
8 as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

9 Citations

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